

Corrigendum: Analysis of Increasing Flash Flood Frequency in the Densely Urbanized Coastline of the Campi Flegrei Volcanic Area, Italy

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Edited and reviewed by:

Davide Tiranti,
Agenzia Regionale per la Protezione
Ambientale (ARPA), Italy

*Correspondence:

Fabio Matano
fabio.matano@cnr.it

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Giuseppe Esposito¹, Fabio Matano^{1*} and Germana Scepi²

¹ Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto Ambiente Marino Costiero, Naples, Italy, ² Dipartimento di Scienze Economiche e Statistiche, Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Naples, Italy

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In the original article, there was a mistake in (Figures 3, 4) as published. Some axis labels were missing and the graphical resolution was low. The corrected (Figures 3, 4) appears below. The authors apologize for this error and state that this does not change the scientific conclusions of the article in any way.

The original article has been updated.

Conflict of Interest Statement: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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FIGURE 3 | Cumulated annual rain at the Pozzuoli rain gauge.

FIGURE 4 | Daily rain time series measured by the Pozzuoli rain gauge.